

Supplementary Material

Table S1. Primers of genes of interest for RT-qPCR.

Gene name	GenBank number	Primer sequences (5'-3')		Product size (bp)
		Forward	Reverse	
Hsd11b2	NM_008289.2	TCCAAGGCAGCAATAGCACT	TCACATTAGTCACTGCATCTGTC	118
Prol1	NM_008644.2	ATCTCCTACCCAGGAGCAACA	TGATGACTTCACCAGGCATGA	99
Il13ra2	NM_001306059.1	GAATGTTGGGAAGAGCCTCCA	CTGCTGGCTGGCTCTATGT	104
Pycard	NM_023258.4	ACTGTGCTTAGAGACATGGGC	TGGTCCACAAAGTGTCTGTT	134
Klotho	NM_013823.2	TGACAACTACGTTCAAGTGGACA	CTTCTTGGCTACAACCCCGT	118
Atf3	NM_007498.3	GAGTGCCTGCAGAAAGAGTCA	CGGTGCAGGTTGAGCATGTAT	116
Nrf2	NM_001399226.1	TCTGCTGCAAGTAGCCTCG	TGGGCAACCATCACTCTGCT	115
CAT	NM_009804.2	ATGGTCACCGGCACATGAAT	GCCCTGGTCGGTCTTGTAAT	104
β -actin	NM_007393.5	CCAGCCTTCCTTCTTGGGTAT	GGGTGTAAAACGCAGCTCAG	374